

THE EFFECTS OF DIGITAL REVOLUTION IN PERSONAL TRADITIONAL BANKING

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The prime objective of the study is to explain the concept of IoT in Banking services and also explain the variety of possibilities opens up particularly in the retail banking sector with the use of IoT in banking sector.

Design/Research Methodology/approach: The whole analysis is based on secondary data collected from different journals, published reports, books, magazines and relevant official website.

Findings: This study is conceptual in nature. It has been found that IoT has opens several opportunities to the banking sector to come out from their traditional method of operating at one hand. And on the other hand, the IoT has created the privacy and security issues of the customers.

Research Implications: This study throws light on the significant contribution of IoT in banking sector. It has drawn attention of the practitioners and policy makers and they are forced to implement IoT in their day to day banking operation particularly in retail banking.

Scope for future work / Research limitations: As this study is based on secondary data. A thorough study based on primary data using quantitative and qualitative method may contribute more fruitful and generalizable results.

Originality/value: The descriptive analysis based on secondary data has found that there are various studies on IoT and its impact on different technical sectors. The paper describes how IoT has benefitted customers and bankers in the retail banking services operation.

Key Words: Retail banking, IoT, digitisation of banking, Banking of thing

Paper type: Conceptual paper

INTRODUCTION

Before the advent of computers, banking operations which were then basically confined to retail banking involved a lot of paper work and required the maintaining large number of physical files (Prachi Mittal, 2013). Transfer of money from one bank to another was an even more difficult task as documents had to be transmitted through the postal system (Karl, 1983). All these changed in the early 1970's with the advent of computers, which were used to store bank related data in an organized manner. Telex and subsequently SWIFT networks were used to send/transfer information related to money transfer, from one bank to another (Dörny et al., 2018).

The emergence of internet further revolutionized the banking industry giving it greater flexibility and efficiency. It enabled banks to step outside the traditional retail banking

business and venture into new areas like financial intermediation, money management, investment banking, etc. (Dilley, 2008) However, the advent of computer and internet technology did not eliminate human labour totally. Substantial human labour was still necessary to enter or rather input raw data into the computer/internet. That is however beginning to change with the emergence of a new generation of internet technology called as Internet of Things (IoT). Under this technology, a large number of objects/things which can collect data, process the collected data and also communicate the same to other objects/things without human intervention are inter-connected together. This technology is now being used in banking to provide innovative real-time financial and other related services to the banking customers. When IoT is used in the banking sector, it is called as Banking of Things (BoT).

OBJECTIVE

This article briefly explains the concept of IoT and the variety of possibilities, it opens up for the banking sector, particularly in the retail banking sector.

EXPLAINING INTERNET OF THINGS

The term Internet of Things (IoT) was coined by Englishman Kevin Ashton in 1999 (DuBravac & Carlo Ratti, 2015), when he was a member of Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) development community (Patel et al., 2016). However, some basic systems based on technology similar to IoT was implemented many years prior to 1999. For example, in the early 1980's, a refrigerated Coca Cola Machine in Carnegie Melon University, USA was connected to a remote computer through the Internet. This remote computer would monitor the availability and temperature of the Coca Cola drink without human intervention (Agger & Westerfield, 1923; Kiranmai & Sridharan, 2017). The present day IoT is a logical extension of Coca Cola machine experiment.

Internet of Things are internet-based networks that facilitate the interconnection of 'things' for the purpose of enabling the sensing and reporting of real world information without human intervention (Abdul-Qawy et al., 2015; Hussain, 2017). 'Thing' in this context is either an object in the physical world (physical thing) or an object in the information world (virtual thing). These objects are capable of being identified and integrated into the communication networks (Villamil et al., 2020). The physical objects are fitted with sensors which measures/monitor various elements in their physical environment like temperature, light, humidity etc and converts them into electronic or virtual information/data which is capable of being transmitted and stored in the virtual world. This virtual information can also be processed and analysed in real-time. Hence IoT is capable of providing reliable real-time intelligence for the purpose of planning, management and quick decision making (Patel et al., 2016).

The uniqueness of IoT is that it provides data capture, computing capabilities and network connectivity to physical objects which are otherwise normally not considered as computers (Rose et al., 2015). Since IoT operates in real time and without any human involvement, IoT adds a new third 'Any Thing' communication dimension to the existing 'Any Time' and 'Any Place' communication dimensions already provided by the existing information and communication technologies (Villamil et al., 2020). Taking advantage of

these newly acquired capabilities of ‘things’, IoT offers a range of services in the filed of banking, transportation, security, smart homes, health care, agriculture, waste management, etc. (Ramalingam & Venkatesan, 2019; Sun et al., 2017). Thus, in short IoT is a network in which a large number of things/objects/sensors/devices are connected together through the internet/ICT infrastructure for the purpose of providing value added services in real time (Lande et al., 2018).

IoT technology is not based solely on hardware or software but on a combination of the two. The hardware components like sensors collects data. The said data is stored in hardware-based memory devices. The data is also transported from one physical location to another using various hardware components of the internet like modem, WiFi, etc. The data so collected, stored and transported using hardware components are usually processed and analysed using various software tools (Patel et al., 2016). The processed data is used for the purpose of enabling value added services.

IoT in Banking

In the last few years, banks around the world have been increasing adopting technologies based on IoT for banking purposes. This is because banks have realized that IoT has the potential to provide a variety of services to customers with very little human intervention and at very little cost (Ramalingam & Venkatesan, 2019). When IoT is used in conjunction with banking it is sometimes referred to as BoT (Banking of Things) (Mistry, 2019). The advent of BoT has given the bank three new key roles namely (a) custodian of customer data (b) financial advisor and (c) payments manager (Mistry, 2019).

IoT permits banks to offer many new services to the customer. Some of the major IoT enabled services offered by the bank to its customers are:

- (a) Digital onboarding: - Onboarding is the process of enrolling a new customer by the bank. This is a complex process, that requires a proper verification and identification of the customer. Traditionally, enrolling a new customer was a face-to-face affair, whereby the customer was required to visit a physical branch of the bank (Adomavicius et al., 2017). However, with the use of IoT, the process of customer onboarding can be completed online without any human intervention. IoT devices can identify/verify a customer’s identity through their biometric data which is already stored in government databases like Aadhar (Martin, 2017).
- (b) Electronic surveillance system for banking: - IoT devices installed at different locations can in real-time without human assistance detect intruders and fraudsters by sensing and analysing data. This enables banks to quickly respond to these issues thereby preventing loss to both the customer and the bank (Ramalingam & Venkatesan, 2019).
- (c) Block chain in banking: - A blockchain is a decentralised distributed ledger that is stored in different devices/locations instead of centralised location. As it is a ledger managed by different devices situated at different locations, it is difficult to alter data as the consent of all devices is necessary (Ramalingam & Venkatesan, 2019). Further, when implementing KYC (Know Your Customer), blockchain can be used by banks

to maintain a common decentralized database of customers. This helps banks save billions of rupees of money (Agrawal et al., 2019).

- (d) Branchless banking (Mobile Banking): - The use of IoT, has enabled customers to avail banking services like money transfer, obtaining account related information, etc. instantaneously without visiting a traditional human operated physical branch of a bank which involves face-to-face interaction between the bank employee and customer (Kiranmai & Sridharan, 2017). If physical cash is required the customer need to only visit a local Automatic Teller Machine (ATM) anytime twenty-four hours a day. IoT has made it possible for customers to access banking services online using various forms of digital interfaces like ATMs, Mobile Apps, Web Access, etc. The digital identity verification of the customer required to enable him to access banking services through a digital interface is facilitated by IoT. Biometric sensors identify the unique digital characteristic of the customer before providing him access to banking services (Khanboubi et al., 2019).
- (e) Personal financial management services: - One of the most promising applications of IoT in banking is the option of Personal Financial Management (PFM) services that banks can offer to its customers with very minimal human intervention. The IoT devices can monitor the investment and spending habits of the customers and based on the analysis of that data, offer customers advices that can help them take sound financial decisions (Infosys, 2018). Similarly, IoT devices can capture data relating to the facial expression of customers visiting the physical branch of the bank. A proper analysis of that data can be used for judging the retail experience of the customer (Ramalingam & Venkatesan, 2019). As IoT technology improves, the future generation of personal financial management tools will enable banks to offer a wide variety of customised services to their customers (Khanboubi et al., 2019).
- (f) Better facilities for customers: - The ever growing use of mobile phones and other wireless devices like wearables by customers has made it possible for banks to offer new innovative services and facilities through IoT (Dineshreddy & Gangadharan, 2016). For example, banks can help their customers belonging to the agricultural sector by using IoT technology. For that purpose, banks can install IoT devices in the farms of their agricultural customers. Those IoT devices will collect crop related data, which will enable the banks to estimate the crop yield. Based on these estimates, bank can offer credit to farmers at flexible rates (Infosys, 2018).
- (g) Capacity management: - IoT enabled devices are used to monitor the number of customers visiting the branch/ATM of a bank. This data is then used to automatically determine how personnel must be deployed in a branch. The same data can also be used to determine whether to open a new branch/ATM or close down existing branch/ATM (Vijay, 2019).
- (h) Bank as payment manager: - The ever-increasing use of smart phones and other such devices by people has enabled the transition from a paper cash economy to cashless economy. Payments are made online directly from the bank account of the customer. The emergence of IoT will add a new dimension to the role of bank as a payment

manager as the need of human intervention in the entire process is eliminated (Mistry, 2019).

Advantages of Banking of Things

The use of IoT in banking is advantageous for both bank and customers. Some of the merits of BoT is outlined below:

1. The customer data collected by the IoT devices when properly analysed enables the banks to better understand the customer and his financial needs (Kiranmai & Sridharan, 2017).
2. The two chief functions of IoT are to capture data using sensors and to transmit that data through the Internet. In the last two decades, the cost of sensors has rapidly declined. Similarly, during the same period, the reliability of internet has improved and its user charges have rapidly fallen. All this has resulted in IoT enabled services being very cost effective (DuBravac & Carlo Ratti, 2015).
3. IoT enables banks to provide real-time services to customers without the customer having to come to the physical branch of the bank (Kiranmai & Sridharan, 2017).
4. IoT permits increased security through encryption and authentication that allow access to banking services to only authorised persons including recognised customers (Kiranmai & Sridharan, 2017).
5. IoT enables banks to monitor customer experience and provide personalised financial services (Khanboubi et al., 2019).
6. IoT devices enables banks to monitor banking frauds on a real-time basis (Infosys, 2018).
7. The use of IoT technology to collect data using hardware and analyse the same using software has enabled banks to reduce their staff strength and thereby increase their profits (Vijay, 2019).

Issues and Concerns

The implementation of IoT technology in banking services has raised a number of concerns and issues. These are very briefly outlined below:

1. IoT devices which facilitate banking services collect data relating to their customers including private information. Ensuring the privacy of the collected data is a real security challenge (Infosys, 2018).
2. IoT devices generate a lot of data. This data has to be stored, processed and analysed in the real-time twenty-four hours a day. This is an expensive process (Lee & Lee, 2015)
3. The IoT devices and associated networks are prone to attack from cybercriminals/hackers. To protect the IoT network from such attacks it is necessary to implement a number of cyber security measures. This also increases the cost (Ghorbani & Ahmadzadegan, 2018).
4. Banks collect a lot of private information about their customers using IoT devices. The bank has to obtain the consent of the customer. The collected data has to be

protected. Any data breach has serious consequences for both the customer and the bank (Infosys, 2018).

5. The data collected by IoT devices has to be transmitted immediately to the nearest data centre. For this purpose, IoT devices extensively rely on wireless networks. It is a very challenging task to make available wireless network throughout the day without interruption (Anwar, 2017).
6. A large number of IoT devices like sensors are used to detect and collect data. There is a possibility that some of these devices may fail or may collect incorrect data. This will impact the quality of the output (Vijay, 2019).

CONCLUSION

Within ten years of its emergence, IoT has made significant in-roads into the banking sector, making available a wide variety of new innovative banking and financial services to customers at minimum cost. The use of IoT in banking has also reduced the need to physical banking branches. It has also reduced the role of human decision making in the banking process. It has also helped to improve the relationship between the bank and the customer. At the same time, use of IoT in banking have raised a number of concerns including privacy which have to adequately tackled if banking of things (BoT) has to be successful.

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